

Figure S1. Pipeline for pseudo-reference genomes produced using the *N. lecontei* reference genome and short-read data from 19 additional species.

a) All SNPs and 1 SNP per kb

b) 1 SNP per 5kb and 1 SNP per 10kb

c) 1 SNP per 50kb

d) 1 SNP per 100kb

Figure S2. *Neodiprion* species trees estimated via SVDquartets. a) Consensus species tree for all SNPs and SNPs subsampled every 1,000 base pairs, **b)** consensus species tree for SNPs sampled every 5 kb or 10 kb, **c)** species tree for SNPs sampled every 50,000 bp, and **d)** species tree for SNPs sampled every 100 kb. Colors correspond to the named species complexes in Fig. 1. Values above each branch are site concordance factors estimated in IQ-TREE, with order in (a) and (b) as indicated in the figure legend.

Figure S3. Riparian plot depicting syntenic collinear blocks for chromosome-level genome assemblies for 4 *Lecontei* group species. Annotated gene sets for each of the four chromosome-level genomes were used to identify orthologous groups across the four *Neodiprion* species. Syntenic collinear blocks of orthologous genes show a high degree of collinearity except for one inversion in Chromosome 1 that differentiates *N. lecontei* and *N. pinetum* from *N. fabricii* and *N. virginiana*. The inversion on Chromosome 1 supports the uniform site concordance values for some clades. Structural polymorphisms are notably absent in Chromosome 7, though analysis of syntenic relationships with additional species may reveal barriers to gene flow in other taxa. To identify orthologous groups, the longest protein isoform for each gene for each species was identified using AGAT (Dainat 2022), which resulted in a set of protein sequences for each species. The four protein sets served as the input for OrthoFinder (Emms and Kelly 2015, 2017, and 2019) to identify orthologous groups, and the OrthoFinder results were assembled into collinear blocks using MCScanX (Wang et al. 2012) and visualized using GENESPACE (Lovell et al. 2022).

Figure S4: Genetic map and local recombination rate for chromosomes 1-4. Panels on the left depict the relationship between physical distance and genetic distance, with individual markers shown as blue dots and model fitted via sliding windows (dotted line). Panels on right depict the recombination rate (cM/Mb) as a function of physical distance.

Figure S5: Genetic map and local recombination rate for chromosomes 5-7. Panels on the left depict the relationship between physical distance and genetic distance, with individual markers shown as blue dots and model fitted via sliding windows (dotted line). Panels on right depict the recombination rate (cM/Mb) as a function of physical distance.

Figure S6: Correlation matrix for genomic predictors of concordance estimated in 50-kb windows. From left-to-right and top-to-bottom, predictors are: number of parsimony-informative sites, number of singletons, proportion missing data, GC content, gene count, and recombination rate (cM/MB). All values are normal-quantile transformed to better visualize relationships between variables. Below the diagonal: pairwise scatter plots; above the diagonal: Pearson's correlation coefficient and significance ($***P < 0.001$; $**P < 0.01$; $*P < 0.05$; $.P < 0.10$); on the diagonal: distributions for variables.

Supporting references

- Dainat J. AGAT: Another Gff Analysis Toolkit to handle annotations in any GTF/GFF format. (Version v0.8.0). Zenodo. <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3552717>
- Emms DM, Kelly S. 2015. OrthoFinder: solving fundamental biases in whole genome comparisons dramatically improves orthogroup inference accuracy. *Genome Biology* 16:157.
- Emms DM, Kelly S. 2017. STRIDE: Species Tree Root Inference from Gene Duplication Events. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 34:3267-3278.
- Emms DM, Kelly S. 2019. OrthoFinder: phylogenetic orthology inference for comparative genomics. *Genome Biology* 20:238.
- Wang YP, Tang HB, DeBarry JD, Tan X, Li JP, Wang XY, Lee TH, Jin HZ, Marler B, Guo H, *et al.* 2012. MCScanX: a toolkit for detection and evolutionary analysis of gene synteny and collinearity. *Nucleic Acids Research* 40.
- Lovell JT, Sreedasyam A, Schranz ME, Wilson M, Carlson JW, Harkess A, Emms D, Goodstein DM, Schmutz J. 2022. GENESPACE tracks regions of interest and gene copy number variation across multiple genomes. *eLife* 11:e78526.